

Type II Glutaric Aciduria, case report

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CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

Abstract: Inborn errors of metabolism are a group of diseases that converge in the presence of mutations expressed in enzymes, transport proteins, among others, that generate a blockage in the metabolism pathways triggering biochemical alterations.

Glutaric aciduria type II is an alteration in the oxidation of fatty acids and amino acids, which includes disorders from severe neonatal presentation to a mild disease in childhood or adulthood with episodic metabolic decompensation, muscle weakness and respiratory failure.

Case report: We present a 32-week preterm newborn with respiratory distress, who presents with initially decompensated metabolic acidosis, maintaining a normal anion gap throughout his hospitalization. The present case corresponds to a neonatal onset phenotype without congenital anomaly in a premature infant. Clinically the patient presented with tachypnea, refusal to feed, but it was the biochemical alterations that pointed to a metabolic cause, due to decompensated metabolic acidosis plus hyperlactacidemia, leukopenia and hypoglycemia. The diagnostic confirmation of glutaric aciduria type II is obtained through the analysis of mutations and the presence of organic acids in urine evidences elevations of dicarboxylic acids, creatine kinase, glutaric acids, ethylmalonic acid, 3-hydroxyisovaleric acid, 5-hydroxyethoxanoic acid, acylglycines, among others.

Neonatal screening should be one of the essential preventive-assistance programs in Public Health, a pillar for the early diagnosis of innate deficiencies in metabolism, which would allow timely intervention and the prevention of metabolic decompensation and possible associated sequelae, both leading to a better prognosis. The suspicion of a metabolic disease, in the presence of nonspecific, progressive signs and symptoms, and once other possible causes have been ruled out, is an advantageous approach to an early diagnosis and prompt therapeutic establishment, a fact that motivated the presentation of this clinical case.

Keywords: Coffin-siris syndrome; Genetic testing;

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